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Comparative Analysis of Different Mathematical Modeling Techniques Approach to Ebola Virus During The 2014 West Africa Outbreak

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ABSTRACT

Models can be useful in estimating important epidemiological parameters from the outbreak data and also be used for the preparedness and moderation planning of future epidemics retrospective analysis in support of policy development. It is important to choose the modelling procedure, to plan the model structure and epidemiological assumptions and parameters. Most of the models in epidemiology are compartmental and based on systems of differential equations, reflecting disease dynamics and rates at which population move from one epidemiological state or compartment to another. The objective of this research work is to collect the data from the published journal articles of different modelling techniques during the 2014 West Africa Ebola virus outbreak online and run a simulation by applying Euler method and compare the result obtain with the finding of the other researchers. Also analyse and interpret the result and see how accurate the method applied when compare with to other method. Make remark on accuracy, similarity or differences where possible between the method applied and techniques. We modelled Ebola virus using the Euler techniques which follows SEIR model, we programme the sequence in to excel with the parameters values and we set the spreadsheet up for Euler method and perform the iteration process on excel and run a simple simulation to produce the graph. This modelled consider the Ebola virus outbreak of West Africa 2014, as an outcome of the modelling the SEIRD. The model has clearly show that 99% of the total population was susceptible. That is, who are not yet infected, while over 60% of the entire population were exposed to the EBOV during the epidemic and about 41% were infected between ten to fifteen days. The exposure reach it maximum peak of about 60% and the graph clearly shows that the number of people that recovered were equal to those who dies as a result of Ebola virus that is (50%) respectively. Similarly the second model SEIHFR indicated that about 95% were susceptible to Ebola virus. In this case, very low cases exposure and infectious which are about 20% and 10% respectively. Besides, the SEIHFR model revealed the unprecedented recovery rate of about 120% as shown in the Figure 4. And finally the result of the two models indicate that both the expose and infectious has banish after forty days. In conclusion we found out that about 50% and above of the infected individuals dies as a result of Ebola virus infection. This can be seen from the model result obtained by the used of Euler method and the disease spread more quickly if control measure is not being put in time. We also found out that Ebola virus disease is an acute fatal infectious disease caused by a filo virus disease and is characterized by a high fever progressing, in many cases, to severe hemorrhage and /or multi- organ failure called Ebola Virus Disease.

Keywords: Ebola virus infection, Euler method, retrospective analysis

INTRODUCTION

Mathematical model can be used to identify the spread of infectious disease in a community and understand infectious dynamics; any time an outbreak of communicable disease occurs, to forecast characteristics of the outbreak, models can be used. For example, size and duration of the outbreak to build epidemic scenarios and model the impact of possible interventions. Mathematical modeling helps in guidance to control strategies and policy decisions. Models can also be useful in estimating important epidemiological parameters from the outbreak data and also be used for the preparedness and moderation planning of future epidemics retrospective analysis in support of policy development. It is important to choose the modeling procedure, to plan the model structure and epidemiological assumptions and parameters. Basically, two main types of model are commonly distinguished. These include deterministic and non-deterministic or stochastic. Most of the models in epidemiology are compartmental and based on systems of differential equations reflecting diseases dynamics and rates at which population move from one epidemiological state or compartment to another. Either deterministic or stochastic can be one of the compartmental models. Background of the study: The recent outbreak of Ebola in West Africa 2014 spread over a largest geographical area and result in the greatest number of infection and death. Unlike preceding epidemics, the Ebola virus of 2014 spread to densely populated areas, which enhance the risk of international spread. In this research a comparative analysis of different mathematical modeling techniques approaches to Ebola virus outbreak in West Africa 2014 was carried out .Method: The transmission of Ebola Virus follows SEIR (susceptible-expose- infectious- recovered) dynamics and can be described by a set of ordinary differential equations (ODEs). Such set of ordinary differential equations are solved by the use of Euler techniques which give a sequence of approximations and was program in to Excel along with the parameter values and produce graphical result or chart. The quantitative data was collected from different journals and used the Euler method to run a simulation and compare the result of the modelling with original result obtained in Guinea, Liberia, Sierra Leon and find out which of the modelling technique involved is more accurate when compared with the result obtain by Euler techniques. Hence, look at the advantages and disadvantages of each model.

Statement of the Problem

With increase in communicable diseases around the world and other pathogenic diseases like Ebola virus, flu, such as A/ H1N1, Swine flu etc. It became necessary, to come out with a way to contain the spread of the disease among the populated communities. So as to avoid further spread and higher mortality. Ebola Virus as one of the latest pandemic in 2014 which cover a larger geographical area around the world, with about 90% cases in West Africa. This lead to introduction of different modeling technique to help in reducing the effect and even eradicating of the disease among the affected communities.

Objective of the Study

- i. To collect the data from published journal articles of different modelling techniques during the 2014 West Africa Ebola virus outbreak online and run simulation by applying Euler method.
- ii. Use Euler method to compare the result obtain with the finding of other researchers.
- iii. To analyse and interpret the result and see how accurate the method applied compare to other method.
- iv. Make remark on accuracy, similarities or differences where possible between the method and techniques if exist

LITERATURE REVIEW

West Africa experienced an Ebola epidemic, the march 23, 2014 was an unprecedented outbreak of a viral hemorrhagic fever. The Global Alert and respond Network, announced that an outbreak of Ebola virus disease in guinea was unfolding said “World Health Organization”. Generally Ebola can be classified as unpredictable instance, the primary rural out breaks, has not been seen in West Africa, in an alarming rate of this magnitude, (Rivers *et al.*, 2014). The World health Organization (WHO) Has also reveals that 8,023 cases of Ebola virus disease in Sierra Leone, Liberia, Guinea, Nigeria and Senegal, with

unpredictable instances accruing outside West Africa (Rivers *et al.*, 2014). A significant attention centre on the preventing the epidemic from spreading further, among West African countries or internationally, in essence, many tactical man oeuvre to contain the spread of Ebola, these involve intensive tracing of any individual person in contact with infected person and the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) for healthcare personal treating of infected person are straight forward (Rivers *et al.*, 2014). In her report 'World Health Organization' point out that implementing those interventions in a resource poor setting in the midst of an ongoing epidemic is far from simple and subject to a great deal of uncertainty (Rivers *et al.*, 2014).

Mathematical models of disease epidemic provide assistance under these situation by giving some useful forecasts for development of the outbreak that account for the complex and non Linear dynamics of contagious disease and protecting the possible impact of proposed interventions before they are implemented. As a result it provides policy makers, the media healthcare personnel and the public health community with timely, quantifiable guidance and support (Rivers *et al.*, 2014). They use of mathematical model to outline the advancement of the Ebola outbreak to date, giving a useful short term prediction for its future broadening and study the possible outcome of various interventions which include, increase contact tracing, right to PPE for healthcare personnel and the use of a pharmaceutical intervention to better for survival in hospitalized patients (Rivers *et al.*, 2014).

To minimize the spread of infectious disease, it is absolutely essential and worthy to quarantine each individual who is likely been expose for a sufficient time for either transmission to occur or until it can be guarantee that there is no probability of transmission. Stated by the centre for Disease Control and Prevention (Haas. 2014). In a situation where somebody has been exposed to an infectious disease and he or she is not yet known whether they have been caught the disease in this case quarantine or separation from others who have not been exposed to the disease is necessary. People who are exposed may be ask to stay or remain in their respective residences to avoid further possible spread of the diseases. A special care and attention for early symptoms of the disease should be granted (Haas 2014). Person who has been exposed to Ebola (EBOV) normally go through a latent period of 2- 21 days before becoming contagious Stadler *et al.*, (2014). After infection, patients either die between 6 and 16 days or may begin to recover within 6 and 11 days (Stadler *et al.*, 2014).

Person who has been exposed to Ebola (EBOV) normally go through a latent period of 2- 21 days before becoming contagious Stadler *et al.*, (2014). After infection, patients either die between 6 and 16 days or may begin to recover within 6 and 11 days (Stadler *et al.*, 2014). The sequential of the virus Gene resulting the outbreak of 2014 has exhibit 98% homology with the Zaire Ebola virus. The fatality ratio (CFR) reached 55% all over the affected countries (Gomes *et al.*, 2014). Licensed treatments foe (EVD) are not available several affected individual can only be cared for with intensive supporting care. (Gomes *et al.*, 2014 and Stadler *et al.*, 2014). It was also been confirmed that 2014 West Africa (EBOD) epidemic is the largest ever seen both by number of infectious cases and areas covered Ebola virus disease world-wide (Gomes *et al.*, 2014 and Stadler *et al.*, 2014).

The overall basic reproductive number of the outbreak in the region is estimated to be in the range of 1.5- 2.0 (Gomes *et al.*, 2014). Similarly (Rivers *et al.*, 2014 and Althaus 2014) states that the basic reproductive number R_0 range between 1.5 to 2.67 in Sierra Leone.

(Yamin *et al.*, 2014) the number of cases in Liberia surpass all the Ebola cases treatment unit by August 2014. Yamin *et al.*, (2014) rightly points out that, the 2014 public health crisis demonstrate no signs of improvement and the risk for Ebola spreading beyond west Africa continued to rise, it require international action to determine effective approaches to stem transmission of this virus

METHODOLOGY

In this research work data was collected from different relevant published journals that adopted different modeling techniques of Ebola virus disease during the 2014 outbreak. Various author used different modeling techniques to analyses the Ebola virus disease. But in this research work Euler method has been used to make a comparative analysis with different methods adopt in the paper. In this research work, a

quantitative analysis has been applied, because it involved numerical data to carry out the comparative analysis.

METHOD

The transmission of Ebola Virus follows SEIR (susceptible-expose- infectious- recovered) dynamics and can be described by the following set of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) (Althaus, 2014).

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -\beta(t)SI/N$$

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \beta(t)SI/N - \sigma E$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \sigma E - \gamma I$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \gamma I - f\gamma I$$

$$\frac{dD}{dt} = f\gamma I$$

Given the above ODEs, has been used to developed a black box or compartmental boxes which indicate the movement of individual from one state of infection to another and also the rate of transmission and recovery during the infectious period. The compartmental boxes below are representing the proportion of individuals at a particular period of time during the infectious period.

Black boxes representing SEIR Model.

Figure 1: compartmental boxes representing the proportion of individuals

Source: Author

After transmission of the virus, susceptible individuals S move to the exposed class E before they become infectious individuals, that either recover and survive R or die D. $1/\sigma$ and $1/\gamma$ are average durations of incubation and infectiousness respectively. The case fatality rate is given by f. The transmission rate in absence of control measures is constant, i.e., $\beta(t) = \beta$. The measures are introduced at a time $\tau \leq t$, the transmission rate was assume to decay exponentially at rate K i.e. $\beta(t) = \beta e^{-k(t-\tau)}$.

‘The Euler method gives the following sequence of approximation of the above ODEs.

$$t_{n+1} = t_{n+h} \Rightarrow " = A5 + \$C\$2"$$

$$S_{n+1} = S_{n+h} (-\beta S_n I_n) \Rightarrow "= B5 - \$C\$2 * (\$E\$1 * B5 * D5)"$$

$$E_{n+1} = E_{n+h} (\beta S_n I_n - \sigma E_n) \Rightarrow "= C5 - \$C\$2 * (\$E\$1 * B5 * D5 - \$G\$1 * C5)"$$

$$I_{n+1} = I_{n+h} (\sigma E_n - \gamma I_n) \Rightarrow " = D5 + \$C\$2 * (\$G\$1 * C5 - \$I\$1 * D5)"$$

$$R_{n+1} = R_{n+h} (\gamma I_n - F\gamma I_n) \Rightarrow " = E5 + \$C\$2 * (\$I\$1 * D5 - \$S\$1 * \$I\$1 * D5)"$$

$$D_{n+1} = D_{n+h} (F\gamma I_n) \Rightarrow " = F5 + \$C\$2 * (\$S\$1 * \$I\$1 * D5)"$$

Basic Assumptions

Let the total population size be $N = S + E + I + D + R$ where;

- i. The susceptible individual exists whom are free of the diseases before exposure S.
- ii. Individual get expose and fall in to expose class i.e. E
- iii. Individual become infected after having contact with the infectious person I.
- iv. Patient dies after infection, D and
- v. Individual recovered after infection, R.

Model Outcome

Figure 2, Source Author

The outcome of the modeling in (figure 2) clearly show that 99% of the total population was susceptible which indicate that 99% of the total population are susceptible to the disease, that is to say they are not yet infected, and over 60% of the entire population were expose to the EBOV during the epidemic and

within one to fifteen days (1 to 15 days) the exposure reach it maximum peak of about 62% of the entire population. Which is clear indication that over 60% were expose to Ebola virus and continue to decline thereafter. Also from the above model figure 5 above, indicated that about 41% were infected with EBOV between (1 to 20 days) of the outbreak, infection attain it highest peak between (1 to 17 days). Similarly, both the number of people recover and die reach up to 50%, this can be seen from the model chart or figure 5, while the recovered curve overlap that of dead curve with tiny yellow line laying beneath the thick blue line which is the clear indication that both recovery and dead are at the same rate which is fifty percent 50%. And this is clear evidence which show that the model is accurate and exhibit a good characteristic of Euler method. In their findings (Althaus 2014, Gomes *et al.*, 2014 and Rivers *et al.*, 2014) rightly points out that over 50% of Ebola virus disease patient experience death. It was also asserted that when the basic reproductive number is larger than approximately (5) five then everyone becomes infected (>99%). Also this can be seen from the model chart or figure 5 above, which indicated over 40% become infected between the first day to seventeen days(1 to 17 days) because the value of R_0 is very higher with estimate of about 21 in the graph of figure 5 above. Both expose and infectious were seen to have vanish after 40 days and this can also be seen from the figure 5 above, which clearly shows both expose and infected curve lies on x axis and vanish after 40 days .

Similarly, the same approach is being adopted in the second modeling techniques, adopted by (Gomes *et al.*, 2014) which has so many compartmental or box and more complex in nature. But in this case, there are different value of gamma, because of presence of additional compartment like H for hospitalised individual, F for funeral and finally R for recovery rate. The presence of this new compartments leads to some movement from one stage to another which give rise to the different gammas thus given the rate at which infectious individual leave one stage to another.

The schematic representation of the compartmental model adopted by (Gomes *et al.*, 2014) to model Ebola virus during the 2014 outbreak is another model we consider to compare with that of (Althaus 2014) using Euler method. This model has six compartments with some parameters either go in or out of the different compartment. The compartments begin with (S) susceptible Individual, exposed individuals (E) infectious cases in the community (I), Hospitalisation cases (H). Both untreated patients in (I) and hospitalized (H) may experience one of two outcomes: patients may die with chance of infecting others during funeral dead but not yet buried (F) before being removed from the model (R) recovered and individuals no longer transmitting the disease.

Below is the compartmental model of (SEIHFR), this model has six compartments:

Black box representing SEIHFR Model

Figure 3: compartmental boxes representing the proportion of individuals
 Source: (Author)

Some of the changes made from the original data during modelling process include numbering of gammas so as help and show which one move from which compartments:

$$\gamma^{-1}_h = \gamma^{-1}_1, \gamma^{-1}_{dh} = \gamma^{-1}_2, \gamma^{-1}_{ih} = \gamma^{-1}_3, \gamma^{-1}_i = \gamma^{-1}_4, \gamma^{-1}_{di} = \gamma^{-1}_5, \gamma^{-1}_f = \gamma^{-1}_6$$

The system of ordinary differential equations describes this model above.

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -\beta SI$$

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \beta SI - \sigma E$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \sigma E - \gamma_1 I - \gamma_4 I - \gamma_5 I$$

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = \gamma_1 I - \gamma_2 H - \gamma_3 H$$

$$\frac{dF}{dt} = \gamma_2 I + \gamma_5 H - \gamma_6 F$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \gamma_4 I + \gamma_3 H + \gamma_6 F$$

The Euler method gives the following sequence of approximation of the above ODEs.

$$t_{n+1} = t_{n+h} \Rightarrow A5 + \$C\$2$$

$$S_{n+1} = S_{n+h} (-\beta S_n I_n) \Rightarrow B5 - \$C\$2 * (\$E\$1 * B5 * D5)$$

$$E_{n+1} = E_{n+h} (\beta S_n I_n - \sigma E_n) \Rightarrow C5 - \$C\$2 * (\$E\$1 * B5 * D5 - \$G\$1 * C5)$$

$$I_{n+1} = I_{n+h} (\sigma E_n - \gamma_1 I_n - \gamma_4 I_n - \gamma_5 I_n) \Rightarrow$$

$$" = D5 + \$C\$2 * (\$G\$1 * C5 - \$I\$1 * D5 - \$O\$1 * D5 - \$Q\$1 * D5)"$$

$$H_{n+1} = H_{n+h} (\gamma_1 I_n - \gamma_2 H_n - \gamma_3 H_n) \Rightarrow$$

$$" = E5 + \$C\$2 * (\$I\$1 * D5 - \$K\$1 * E5 - \$M\$1 * E5)"$$

$$F_{n+1} = F_{n+h} (\gamma_2 I_n + \gamma_5 H_n - \gamma_6 F_n) \Rightarrow " = F5 + \$C\$2 * (\$K\$1 * D5 + \$Q\$1 * E5 - \$S\$1 * F5)"$$

$$R_{n+1} = R_{n+h} (\gamma_4 I_n + \gamma_3 H_n + \gamma_6 F_n)$$

$$\Rightarrow " = G5 + \$C\$2 * (\$O\$1 * D5 + \$M\$1 * E5 + \$S\$1 * F5)"$$

We program this sequence in to excel with the parameter listed below:

Let the total population be size $N = S + E + I + H + F + R$ where;

$$S_0 = 0.920,$$

$$E_n = 0$$

$$I_n = 0.01$$

$$H_n = 0.05$$

$$F_n = 0.03$$

$$R_n = 0 \text{ and}$$

The following transition parameters used for Euler method were obtain from(Rivers *et al.*, 2014 & Gomes *et al.*, 2014)

The mean time from on set to hospitalisation is 3.24 days

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma_h} = \frac{1}{\gamma_1} = 3.24 \text{ days} \Rightarrow \gamma_1 = \frac{1}{3.24} \text{ days} = 0.3086$$

Mean time from hospitalisation to death.

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma_{dh}} = \frac{1}{\gamma_2} = 10.07 \text{ days} \Rightarrow \gamma_2 = \frac{1}{10.7} \text{ days} = 0.0993$$

Mean time from hospitalisation to the end of infectiousness for survival.

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma_{ih}} = \frac{1}{\gamma_3} = 15.88 \text{ days} \Rightarrow \gamma_3 = \frac{1}{15.88} \text{ days} = 0.0629$$

Mean time from onset to the end of infectiousness for survival.

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma_i} = \frac{1}{\gamma_4} = 15 \text{ days} \Rightarrow \gamma_4 = \frac{1}{15} \text{ days} = 0.0667$$

Mean time from on set to death

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma_{di}} = \frac{1}{\gamma_5} = 13.31 \text{ days} \Rightarrow \gamma_5 = \frac{1}{13.31} \text{ days} = 0.07513$$

Mean time from death to traditional burial.

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma_f} = \frac{1}{\gamma_6} = 2.01 \text{ days} \Rightarrow \gamma_6 = \frac{1}{2.01} \text{ days} = 0.4975$$

Mean time/ duration of incubation period.

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\sigma} = 12 \text{ days} \Rightarrow \sigma = \frac{1}{12} \text{ days} = 0.1887. \text{ (Rivers } et al., 2014 \& \text{ Gomes } et al., 2014).$$

The Euler method gives the sequence of approximation of the above ordinary differential equations (ODEs). These will be programme in to excel together with the parameters values above obtain from (Rivers *et al.*, 2014 & Gomes *et al.*, 2014). We use a spreadsheet and run a simple simulation in to excel to produce the graph in figure below. The graph produce by Euler method.

Figure 4.
Source Author

Comparison With Real Data Result

The original data obtain from (Althaus *et al.*, 2014) were retrieved from the (WHO) website of and based on the cumulative total number of clinical cases, (confirmed, probable and suspected). On 27 may 2014 the first confirmed cases in Sierra Leone were reported. In Liberia, the cases that were report on 16 June 2014 were the first new cases since 6 April 2014 (Althaus *et al.*, 2014). We used the data below to plot the graph and the result can be seen below.

Figure 5.
Source: (Althaus *et al.*, 2014).

Comparing the result obtained from the original data with that obtained by the use of Euler method, and we can see the great similarities in terms of the number of people dies as a result of the infection. About 67% of the infected individual dies (i.e. 406 out of 607 cases) which is close to result obtained by Euler method which gives about 50% death. It can also be seen in the majority of the modelling papers that the fatality rate is more than fifty percent, (Althaus, *et al.*, 2014, Gomes *et al.*, 2014 and Rivers *et al.*, 2014) rightly points out that over 50% of Ebola virus disease patient experience death. This can also be seen in the Sierra Leone outbreak which has the highest cases and death (1082 and 624) respectively and with an approximately 58% death. This can be seen from the diagram produce in figure 7 of Guinea, Sierra Leone and Liberia which shows a similar pattern of infection growth which is in increasing order just like in the previous graph in figure 5 of guinea outbreak that were obtained using the Euler method from 0 up to 400 000 which correspond to that of Guinea. Furthermore, comparing the result obtained from the (SEIHFR) model using of Euler method in Figure 4 one can see that one fifth i.e. 1/5 or in other wards 20% of the whole population are expose and with about one tenth 1/10 or 10% are infected and about 18% of the infected individual are hospitalised with only very few dead or funeral case but recovery show an unprecedented scenario with more than 120% while the number of susceptible stand at about 92%. To me the modelled (SEIHFR) using Euler method seem to be more accurate, because there still some fraction of individuals who are not yet infected. When compare with result obtained from similar modelled (SEIRD) in the graph of Guinea in figure 5 which shows more than 99% or we can say the entire population is susceptible and it also reveals that there was an increase pattern in both infected cases and number of death up to 50%. Consequently, the outcome of the modelled (SEIHFR) using the Euler method cannot be compare with result obtained from the original data of both Guinea, Liberia and Sierra Leon outbreak which was already plotted in figure 6, because there were very few number of both exposure and infectious cases with very few number of hospitalisation and unprecedented higher number of recovery and also with very few number of death of not more than 10% as indicated in the modelled result chart, which does not characterised the Ebola virus in which mostly resulted in about or more than 50% of the infected population.

STRENGTH AND WEAKNESS OF THE MODELS

Both the two model has their strength and weakness, the first model which is the (SEIRD) indicate that more than 99% of the population were susceptible, which means that the entire population were susceptible of Ebola virus disease which does reflect a good characteristics of SEIR model. But on other part it shows the good features of SEIR model such as the proportion of exposure, infection, recovery and death. However, the second model which is more accurate has clearly shows that there are still a fraction of people who were not infected and are free from the outbreak even though there were unprecedented number of people who recovered from the virus which is about 120%. Thus constituting a strange phenomenon which indicates that there were high proportion of infectious individuals that move into R compartment indicating that they either recovered or die.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion we found out that Ebola virus disease is an acute fatal infectious disease caused by a filo virus disease and is characterized by a high fever progressing, in many cases, to severe hemorrhage and /or multi- organ failure is called Ebola Virus Disease. The disease causing agent is classified as group 4 pathogens. About 50% and above of the infected individuals dies as a result of infection, this can be seen from the model result obtained by the used of Euler method and the disease spread more quickly if control

measure is not being put in time, more compartment were introduces to separate the infected people from further spreading the virus in to the community. Also identifying and isolation of infected individual and place them in the appropriate compartment has reduce the spread of the disease in the community and to better understand the spread of infection in the affected countries, it is equally very important to know the number of secondary cases resulted by an infected individual in the absence of control measures.

In this research work, standard values for ODEs parameters used were obtained from journal articles published during the 2014 West Africa Ebola virus outbreak. The simulations and analysis made are based on these standard values which were obtained from the published articles during 2014 EBOV West Africa outbreak. A quantitative data of different modelling techniques adopted during the 2014 outbreak, were collected and simulations were run using Euler method and we carry out the analysis which allow comparison with the real data by plotting the graph of the original data.

In this research work, we can see that the use of SEIRD and SEIHR Models has helped to reduce and contain the spread of the infection within the community or affected area. Most models used in modeling the 2014 Ebola virus allow quarantine and isolation of infected individual through various means like hospitalizing infected and separating case of dead body to funeral in to different compartments until the last stage of the infection.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

To model the Ebola virus disease we recommend that bigger model should be introduced which will cover larger population size, should in case of emergence of an outbreak in a very densely populated area or big cities. That is, the models which consider different structure to the population than one homogeneous assumption because of the vast area of West Africa, more especially the Ebola virus pandemic areas of 2014 constitute disperse and highly densely populated town and villages. For further future work method like Runge- kutta can be applied to carry out the analysis.

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